

Supplementary Information

Disruption of seasonal influenza circulation and evolution during the 2009 H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemics in Southeastern Asia

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Supplementary Fig. 1 | Illustration of the methodology used to determine the average curve of A/H3N2 positivity rate in the Northern hemisphere for seasons in the interpandemic period. a) A/H3N2 positivity rates over time in the Northern hemisphere. Light and dark red shading denotes the A/H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemic seasons, respectively. **b)** Step 1: Plotting the positivity curve for each season, where the season was defined as running from ISO week 27 of one year to ISO week 26 of the next year. No outlier seasons (defined as a season where the peak positivity rate occurred at the start or end of the season, i.e., ISO week 26 or 27 for the Northern hemisphere) were identified during the interpandemic period. **c)** Step 2: Identifying the median week of peak occurrence (ISO week 1, here) for the seasons in the interpandemic period after removing the outlier seasons, followed by the epidemic alignment of interpandemic seasons. **d)** Step 3: Calculating an average curve for seasons in the interpandemic period.

Supplementary Fig. 2 | Illustration of the methodology used to determine the average curve of A/H3N2 positivity rate in the Southern hemisphere for seasons in the interpandemic period. **a)** A/H3N2 positivity rates over time in the Southern hemisphere (SH). Light and dark red lines denote the A/H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemic seasons, respectively. **b)** Step 1: Plotting the positivity curve for each season, where the season was defined as running from ISO week 1 to week 52 of one year. One outlier season (dark blue line, corresponding to the 2011 season) was identified since the peak positivity rate occurred at the start of the season. The pandemic seasons defined here both spanned across two SH seasons, so black dotted lines (Jan-Jun 2009, Jul-Dec 2010, Jan-Jun 2020, Jul-Dec 2021) are used to refer to curves outside the pandemic influenza seasons. **c)** Step 2: Identifying the median week of peak occurrence (ISO week 32, here) for the seasons in the interpandemic period, after removing the outlier season, followed by the epidemic alignment of interpandemic seasons. **d)** Step 3: Calculating an average curve for seasons in the interpandemic period. The first half of the positivity lines (Jan-Jun 2010; Jan-Jun 2021) during the pandemic periods occurred after the second half of the line (Jul-Dec 2009; Jul-Dec 2020).

Supplementary Fig. 3 | Case incidence and stringency index in Southeastern Asia during the two pandemics. a) Reported cases per million people in Southeastern Asia during the 2009 H1N1 (blue) and COVID-19 (red) pandemics. Data of H1N1pdm09 cases in several sublocations (Bhutan, Brunei, Macao (China), Myanmar, Nepal, Taiwan (China), East Timor) are not available. **b)** Compound airline traffic indicator during the 2009 H1N1 (solid blue line) and COVID-19 pandemics (solid red line) in Southeastern Asia. Pattern consistency of compound airline traffic indicator (solid red line) with the COVID-19 Stringency Index (dashed line) during the COVID-19 pandemic is also shown. The COVID-19 Stringency Index in Southeastern Asia is a population-weighted average among countries.

Supplementary Fig. 4 | Socio-demographic index (SDI) for each sublocation in two pandemic years. SDI is a composite indicator developed by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) and has been shown to be highly correlated with health outcome variables ^{1,2}.

Supplementary Fig. 5 | Temperature and absolute humidity from 2007 to 2023 for each study sub-location in Southeastern Asia. a) Temperature for each sub-location. b) Absolute humidity for each sub-location. Previous work has indicated that temperature and absolute humidity may be the main climatic drivers of seasonal influenza transmission dynamics in the tropics and subtropics ³.

Supplementary Fig. 6 | Importance of variables in the random forest model associated with the decline of influenza activity during the pandemics. a) Importance of variables during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic. **b)** Importance of variables during the COVID-19 pandemic. Error bars show the standard deviations of the variable importance.

Supplementary Fig. 7 | The hierarchical geographic structures used for the sub-sampling process. The smallest sub-sampling unit was in the sub-location level. The entirety of South America was grouped with the southern hemisphere (SH), since the SH vaccine formulation is recommended in this whole area. Spatial boundaries of 22 sub-locations in Southeastern Asia are presented at the bottom.

Supplementary Fig. 8 | A five-week running average of the relative weekly viral movement events of A/H3N2 and B/Victoria between two regions using different sets of genetic data from three sub-sampling schemes. a-c) A/H3N2 weekly movement under three sub-sampling schemes. d-f) B/Victoria weekly movement under three sub-sampling schemes. Light and dark red shading denote the A/H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemic seasons, respectively, between which are inter-pandemic seasons.

Supplementary Fig. 9 | Trunk location probability of A/H3N2 and B/Victoria over time under three sub-sampling schemes. a-c) Trunk location of A/H3N2 under three sub-sampling schemes. d-f) Trunk location of B/Victoria under three sub-sampling schemes.

Supplementary Fig. 10 | Proportion of persistent lineages from July 2009 to June 2021 (2009 H1N1 pandemic, interpandemic, and COVID-19 pandemic seasons) under three sub-sampling schemes. a) Higher proportions of persistent lineages were observed in A/H3N2 than B/Victoria. **b)** Higher proportions of A/H3N2 persistent lineages were observed during the COVID-19 pandemic season compared to the interpandemic period. Statistical comparisons were performed using a chi-square or Fisher's exact test.

Supplementary Fig. 11 | Leading and trailing geographic regions of A/H3N2 and B/Victoria genetic evolution. **a)** Genetic distance from A/Wisconsin/67/2005 of all A/H3N2 virus strains plotted against time of collection. The thick grey line is the fitted line using a LOESS model. Points to the right of the line are antigenically advanced, whereas strains to the left of the line are antigenically lagging. Light and dark red shading denotes the A/H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemic seasons, respectively. **b)** Genetically advanced and lagging months of A/H3N2 by region and period. Here genetically advanced and lagging distances are not presented on the bottom x-axis as it was not in direct proportion to months (LOESS model adopted). Grey oblique squares indicate the average months to the fitted spline for strains isolated in each region. Coloured circles split this overall average by various periods. Size of circles refers to the number of sequences that are used for the estimate. **c)** Same as (a) but for B/Victoria. **d)** Same as (b) but for B/Victoria.

Supplementary Fig 13 | The geographic trunk probability of A/H3N2 persistent lineages circulating in Southeastern Asia. a) Trunk location inferred at 22 sub-location levels. b) Trunk location aggregated at 3 sub-region levels. Trunk was defined as all branches ancestral to viruses sampled within 1 year of the most recent sample. Vertical dashed black lines refer to the A/H1N1 pandemic and COVID-19 pandemic season, respectively.

Supplementary Fig 14 | Border control measures and viral movement of A/H3N2 during the COVID-19 pandemic in mainland China. **a)** Restrictions on international travel controls for foreign travellers (dashed line, only available until the end of 2022), air traffic inflows (red line) and outflows (blue line, which is virtually indistinguishable from the inflows as they are highly consistent) in China. Restrictions on international travel controls were retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/covid-international-domestic-travel>. **b)** Relative viral movement intensity of A/H3N2 subtype within China (i.e., movements between south China, central China, and north China). **c)** Relative viral movement inflows (red line, from other sub-locations in Southeastern Asia to China) and outflows (blue line, from China to other sub-locations in Southeastern Asia) of A/H3N2 subtype in China.

Supplementary Fig. 15 | Airline capacity or passengers over time. a) Total global monthly airline capacity or passengers. Data of airline passengers are not available before 2011, therefore airline capacity data (number of available seats) are used instead; b) Total monthly airline capacity or passengers among countries within Southeastern Asia; c) Total monthly airline capacity or passengers among countries within temperate regions.

Supplementary Fig. 16 | Sequence-based antigenic distance from A/Wisconsin/67/2005 of all virus strains plotted against time of collection using sequence datasets from the other two sub-sampling schemes. a) Distance against time using sequence datasets from population-weighted sub-sampling scheme. **b)** Distance against time using sequence datasets from population and influenza activity-weighted sub-sampling scheme. The thick grey line is the fitted line using a linear model. Points to the right of the line are antigenically advanced, whereas strains to the left of the line are antigenically lagging. Light and dark red shading denotes the A/H1N1 and COVID-19 pandemic seasons, respectively, between which were inter-pandemic seasons.

Supplementary Fig. 17 | Root-to-tip genetic distances plotted against collection dates under three sub-sampling schemes. a-c) Temporal signal of A/H3N2 under three sub-sampling schemes. d-f) Temporal signal of B/Victoria under three sub-sampling schemes. Blue lines are the fitted lines using a linear model, with Pearson correlation coefficients (ρ) reported.

Supplementary Table 1. Characteristics of two pandemics.

	2009 H1N1 pandemic	COVID-19 pandemic	Sources
Case incidence in Southeastern Asia (cases per million people)	Low [#] (Supplementary Fig. 3a)	High (Supplementary Fig. 3a)	4-6
Viral transmissibility (R_0)	1.7	2.5	7
Cross immunity with seasonal influenza virus	High/moderate	Low	8,9
Air travel-related stringency index in Southeastern Asia	Low* (Supplementary Fig. 3b)	High (Supplementary Fig. 3b)	OAG and ¹⁰
Socio-demographic index (SDI) in Southeastern Asia	Low (Supplementary Fig. 4)	High (Supplementary Fig. 4)	2
Humidity	Periodic fluctuation (Supplementary Fig. 5)		European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)
Temperature	Periodic fluctuation (Supplementary Fig. 5)		

[#] The under-ascertainment of the true number of infected individuals during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic is assumed to be more severe than the COVID-19 pandemic due to the limited monitoring capacity.

* Air travel-related stringency indexes during the 2009 H1N1 pandemic in Southeastern Asia use the compound airline traffic indicator as a proxy.

Supplementary Table 2. The Pearson correlation coefficient between compound airline traffic indicator (air travel-related stringency index) and COVID-19 stringency index during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Sub-location	Pearson (ρ)	Sub-location	Pearson (ρ)
Thailand	0.935	Japan	0.769
Philippines	0.931	Hong Kong, China	0.733
India	0.919	Mainland China	0.717
Indonesia-East Timor	0.904	South Korea	0.698
Malaysia-Brunei	0.904	Sri Lanka	0.695
Myanmar	0.878	Laos	0.678
Singapore	0.870	Cambodia	0.629
Bangladesh	0.868	Taiwan, China	0.620
Vietnam	0.860	Bhutan	0.322
Nepal	0.832	Macao, China	0.271

Note: The COVID-19 stringency indexes were only available for mainland China as a whole. Since there is no internal airline traffic in Hong Kong (China), Macao (China) and Singapore, we constructed an indicator with only air travel from/to the sublocation for these three sublocations.

Supplementary Table 3. Statistical test of antigenic distance of A/H3N2 to the fitted line between pandemic season and interpandemic seasons.

Influenza seasons	Southeastern Asia			Temperate regions		
	Distance (Months)*	<i>p</i> value		Distance (Months)	<i>p</i> value	
Interpandemic seasons	0.020 (0.8)	Reference	Reference	-0.054 (-2.3)	Reference	Reference
Pandemic seasons						
2009/2010	0.258 (10.8)	< 0.001 [‡]	-	0.159 (6.7)	< 0.001	-
2020/2021	-0.105 (-4.4)	-	< 0.001	-0.096 (-4.1)	-	0.632

*Average antigenic distance of A/H3N2 virus lineages circulating in specific season and region to the fitted line (**Fig. 4a**), for which the line can also be interpreted as a function of time (months). Positive values refer to antigenically advanced distance (months), whereas negative values refer to antigenically lagging distance (months).

[‡] Comparison of antigenic distance of virus lineages circulating between pandemic season (2009/2010) and all interpandemic seasons (as reference), where a two-sided *p* value was obtained by Bootstrap resampling using 1,000 replicates. Exact *p* values are provided unless they are less than 0.001.

Supplementary Table 4. Correlates of covariates to the relative and overall migrations in Southeastern Asia under the phylogeographic model.

Covariates	Effect size
Dependent variable: relative migration rates*	
Air traffic network matrix	0.954 (0.806-1.116)
Dependent variable: overall migration rate[#]	
Air traffic volume	0.435 (0.322-0.566)

*The product of the log coefficients and the inclusion probabilities is reported as log effect sizes, with posterior mean and 95% HPD intervals summarised.

[#] We parameterize the overall rate scalar as a log-linear function of the overall among-country air traffic volume (we used the air capacity data in 2007-2023 to indicate the air traffic volume in each epoch because there are no air passenger volumes available in 2007-2010), with effect size representing log regression coefficient.

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